

The Show Must Go On: Active Online Collaboration during COVID-19 – Mathematics Students Solving Real-World Problems

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Abstract

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic caught the world off-guard, and the impact of the pandemic is unprecedented. Consequently, universities were closed, and lecturers were forced to adjust their teaching and learning practices and to shift their courses to online learning. This paper reports on Mathematics education students' active practices, experiences and reflections on their online collaboration regarding real-world problems. The aim was to determine how active group work could contribute to students' ability to solve such problems during the pandemic in an online environment. Although a mixed-method approach was employed, the emphasis in this paper is only on aspects of the qualitative phase. A cohort comprising 52 BEd students participated. They worked in 13 groups of four members each. Before students began with the assignments, they were introduced to active teaching-learning approaches, such as problem-based learning and cooperative learning. Group members were required to complete two assignments and submit them on the learning management system. Upon completion, randomly selected students completed task-based questions about their experiences of the assignments, mathematical skills and the type of thinking that they used. Students also had to reflect on the nature of their collaboration, personal interaction, and challenges they experienced. Students further assessed themselves as well as their peers regarding their active involvement and commitment. The data were manually coded and main themes emerged. The findings indicate that students initially experienced challenges with online learning. This learning mode forced them to take responsibility for their assignments, to assist each other in their learning processes, and to work closely as a group to ensure that they solved the problems correctly. The value was that students learned from one another, reflected on their efforts, and developed essential skills. The students enjoyed to work on real-world problems as they could identify with such problems. Social and teacher presence was crucial in the online learning environment. Some insights were gained regarding active online collaboration.

Keywords: Active Learning; Mathematics Students; Online Collaboration; Real-World Problem Solving.

1 Introduction

Albert Einstein said, "[e]ducation is not the learning of many facts but the training of the mind to think" (A-Z Quotes, n.d., n.p.). These famous words imply that learning is not about obtaining information as such, but rather about developing the ability to integrate and apply knowledge meaningfully.

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has adversely affected people across the world and the impact thereof is unprecedented (Del Rio & Malani, 2020). The pandemic forced people to think of new ways to survive and cope under different and challenging circumstances. As a result, universities were closed and it was compulsory for lecturers to adjust their teaching and learning practices and to shift their courses to online learning within a short time (Adedoyin & Soykan, 2020; Mishra, Gupta, & Shree, 2020). It was also expected of residential or contact students to return home and embark on an online journey in their respective courses. Consequently, students were forced to face an online environment – literally and figuratively – in order to pass. Such circumstances contribute to the challenge for students to be successful in their studies.

Succeeding in Mathematics is in itself a challenge for many students (Hasan, 2019). They often view Mathematics as a subject isolated from the real world with limited application in other contexts, such as Physical Science, Life Sciences and Geography (Li & Stylianides, 2018). Possible reasons for this may be traditional teaching approaches to which they had been exposed at school. These approaches often result in rote learning, the use of familiar algorithms, low-level thinking, and preparation for tests and examinations (Lubis, 2021). Students should, however, not only understand mathematical principles, but should also be able to apply them in new and unfamiliar settings (Li & Stylianides, 2018). Moreover, such

activities may help students in developing persistence and confidence as they deal with “ambiguous problems and collaborate and engage in rigorous academic discussions with peers” (Kopcha et al., 2017, p. 32).

In pandemic circumstances, however, it is not necessarily trivial that students will actively collaborate online as they are acquainted with a face-to-face learning context (Jacobs & Ivone, 2020; Lubis, 2021; Scull, Phillips, Sharma, & Garnier, 2020). This paper reports on the online group collaboration of students in a BEd Intermediate Phase Mathematics module. The research was guided by the following research question: *how can active collaboration contribute to mathematics students’ solving of real-world problems in an online environment?*

2 Context and Related Work

The following theoretical aspects are outlined briefly below: active learning, online collaboration, and solving real-world mathematics problems.

2.1 Active Learning

There is consensus that students should be actively involved in their learning and that traditional approaches, such as lectures, are no longer suitable for the development of essential knowledge and skills (Gravett, Yakovchuk, & Kinchin, 2020; Loh & Ang, 2020; Lubis, 2021). In addition, the World Economic Forum (WEF) (2016) highlights that active learning is essential for the future and the Fourth-Industrial Revolution (4IR) demands. Rands and Gansemer-Topf (2017) view active learning as a teaching–learning strategy where students are involved in performing tasks and sharing responsibilities such as active listening, peer questioning and discussing challenging problems in small groups. Active learning involves the facilitation of student collaboration as well as their engagement in problem-solving activities (Farrow & Wetzel, 2020). Through active engagement, students develop knowledge and skills that can enhance their higher-order thinking abilities (Jacobs & Ivone, 2020; Lubis, 2021). Bakar and Ismail (2020) elaborate that active learning encourages students to analyse problems and think logically. Kulikovskikh, Lipic, and Šmuc (2020) also refer to the role of reasoning and humans’ ability in constructing new knowledge. Moreover, reflective thinking is essential. Veine et al. (2020) argue that reflection is a core activity to address complexity and unexpected outcomes, and provides an opportunity to learn from such experiences. Teaching–learning strategies, such as problem-based learning (PBL), project-based learning, cooperative learning (CL) and inquiry-based learning can be used to structure active student participation (Chen, Kolmos, & Du, 2020; Johnson & Johnson, 2019). In addition, learning management systems (LMSs) and platforms provide for students’ engagement in the learning process and their development as self-directed learners (Han, Lim, & Jung, 2021). To summarise, active learning involves:

- *drivers for learning*: craft real-world problems or challenging scenarios and employ, for example, PBL, active collaboration and inquiry-based learning;
- *facilitators of learning*: lecturers plan for an active teaching–learning environment, provide adequate support and constructive feedback;
- *constructors of knowledge*: students actively construct new knowledge;
- *collaborators in learning*: each member contributes to group work, and enhances group dynamics; and
- *technologies for learning*: use a learning environment and technologies to provide for effective student collaboration.

2.2 Online Collaboration

The outbreak of COVID-19 compelled educators worldwide to use emergency remote teaching and learning (Adedoyin & Soykan, 2020; Mishra et al., 2020). The expectation was that online learning would replace face-to-face contact sessions to continue learning during the pandemic (Lubis, 2021). The aim was to have uninterrupted online teaching and learning under disrupted circumstances. Online learning platforms become the *modus operandi* for the delivery of subject matter, communication, and the application of assessment practices (Lubis, 2021). Han et al. (2021) highlight that effective facilitation through a learning management system is essential for online classrooms. Such an environment provides opportunities for students to engage actively in their learning, identify their own learning needs, manage learning responsibilities, reflect on their experiences, and develop as self-directed learners (Han et al., 2021). Collaboration offers students communication opportunities and the benefit of assisting each other, and adds a social component to their learning (Jacobs & Ivone, 2020; Loh & Ang, 2020). D’Alessio et al. (2019, p. 222) found that, when facilitators provide a “supportive community” in an online environment and facilitate students’ collaboration and involvement, students benefit from such interaction. Already in 1995, Berge (p. 22–23) distinguished different types of interaction involved in online tutoring to succeed, namely *pedagogical* interaction (probe students for critical discussion), *social* interaction (promote learning, group members work cohesively and in a “mutual cause”), *managerial* interaction (management of learning), and *technical* interaction (software and technological aspects). Carrillo and Flores (2020) accentuate the importance of the following three presences in an online collaborative environment:

- firstly, *social* presence regarding students' ability to engage effectively, communicate purposefully, and develop interpersonal relationships in a collaborative environment;
- secondly, *teaching* presence, which involves the design, facilitation and guidance of cognitive and social processes to achieve meaningful outcomes; and
- thirdly, *cognitive* presence, which comprises the extent to which students construct meaning through communication and reflection in a community of practice (Carrillo & Flores, 2020).

Online collaboration, when administered effectively, ought to result in establishing the essential three presences, mentioned above (Carrillo & Flores, 2020).

2.3 Solving Real-World Mathematics Problems

Life is a journey to develop practical solutions to many problems. The exposure to real-world problem situations contributes to the development of skills and the preparation for future demands of work (Gravemeijer, Stephan, Julie, Lin, & Ohtani, 2017). Real-world problems must be meaningful, that is, they must match the student's abilities and must be relevant to the cognitive structure of the student (Lubis, 2021; Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD], 2018). Mathematics is considered the language of technology and nature, and is a fundamental subject in many disciplines (Feuerstein & Roubik, 2019). The rationale for learning Mathematics is to enable people to solve problems that are sometimes complex, ill-structured and open-ended (Siagian, Saragih, & Sinaga, 2019). Consequently, students must possess a different set of knowledge, skills and perspectives from those of previous generations, to address the demands of the twentieth century. Such skills are communication, critical and creative thinking, decision-making, reflection, self-direction, collaboration and information literacy (OECD, 2018). Active problem solvers engage in three processes of mathematical reasoning typified by the following verbs: formulate, employ and interpret (OECD, 2018). Firstly, students must recognise the mathematical nature of a problem encountered in the real world and formulate it in mathematical terms. Changing a real-world situation into a well-defined mathematics problem necessitates mathematical reasoning (OECD, 2018). The problem must then be solved by using mathematics procedures, algorithms and concepts. Students also need to evaluate the solution by interpreting the results in terms of the initial situation. However, solving real-world mathematics problems online in COVID circumstances is a challenge for students. Mulenga and Marbán (2020) report on prospective teachers who engaged in online mathematics activities during COVID-19. Some students had positive attitudes towards working online, while others experienced some challenges, for example, they were unfamiliar with online platforms and technologies as well as long hours of connection and internet costs.

The next section reports on whether active group collaboration contributed to mathematics students' solving of real-world problems in an online environment.

3 Research Methodology

This research was initially planned for a face-to-face learning context, but was realised online due to the pandemic. Ethical clearance was obtained from the university and all ethical requirements were adhered to. A mixed-method research design was utilised. However, the emphasis in this paper is on aspects of the qualitative phase. In this research, an active learning approach was followed where participants were responsible for their collaboration and contribution to group work.

3.1 Participants

Participants involved a cohort comprising 52 BEd students enrolled for a second-year general Mathematics module with the aim of teaching future Grade 8 and 9 school learners. This module entails number patterns, algebraic reasoning and functional relationships, with the emphasis on an exploratory and active approach to solving real-world problems. At the beginning of the semester, the researcher randomly placed the students in 13 groups of four members each. Each group selected a group leader themselves and they had to give reasons for choosing the specific leader using a Google Form. The students remained in the same group for the duration of the semester and completed their assignments, while the group leader was responsible for submitting all the assignments online.

3.2 Online Activities

Group collaboration, assignments and data gathering and analysis are set out in this subsection.

3.2.1 Group Collaboration

Due to COVID-19, the module was presented online during the second semester, with all the activities on eFundi, the LMS of the university (refer to Table 1). As part of the preparation and to introduce students to essential skills, each student had to research PBL, active learning and cooperative learning, and submit an assignment based on these topics. However, in an online learning environment (Figure 1), it was a challenge to determine the extent to which students applied these active

learning strategies. Group members had the freedom to decide on their own means of communication. They mainly used email, WhatsApp, Telegram, Facebook and Zoom, and used eFundi to upload their assignments. Since participants were residential students, online cooperation and the activities were challenging and unfamiliar to them, as they were used to working in groups in class. The researcher created one WhatsApp group for the whole class as a means of communication and support. In addition, every group leader created a WhatsApp group to enable direct and effective communication between the group members.

Figure 1. Students' active online collaboration and mathematical problem solving.

3.2.2 Group Assignments

Student activities involved two assignments during the semester (Table 1). Each assignment was uploaded on eFundi, and members had 14 days to complete the assignment as a group. Assignments required algebraic reasoning, problem solving and group decision-making. As part of group work, members had to solve problems where they shared responsibility, accountability, knowledge and skills. Students analysed the problems, gathered and organised relevant information, and presented their solutions together with proof of their argumentation and thinking processes. Each group leader then uploaded the solutions, and the researcher assessed their assignments using a rubric. The university online marking tool was used for assessment. Because of the pandemic, the researcher randomly selected 26 students (13 for each assignment) to individually complete task-based questions on a Google Form. Unfortunately, only 19 students completed these questions, probably because the semester ended and they lost interest. Students had to reflect on the nature of their collaboration in terms of the support from their group members, their responsibility, personal interaction and communication, the challenges that they experienced, and how they managed these. Furthermore, they had to allocate a mark out of 10 for themselves as well as for each of the group members. The online activities as shown in Table 1 below were involved, while Figure 2 gives an indication of all the activities that were followed.

Table 1. Rationale for selecting particular activities.

Assignments	Rationale
1. Individual assignment on PBL, CL & active learning	Introduce students to active teaching–learning strategies
2. Group Assignment 1: Renovating bedroom	Apply formulas in real-life scenarios
3. Individual task-based questions on Assignment 1	Students reflect on the assignment and collaboration
4. Group Assignment 2: Cardboard box specification	Suggest the most economical size of the box
5. Individual task-based questions on Assignment 2	Students reflect on the assignment and collaboration

Figure 2. Diagram of sequential activities involved in this research.

Two assignments with real-world problems were included (Table 1). In the first assignment, students had to provide their parents with a total budget for renovating their bedroom. To do this, they had to determine the most cost-effective way to tile their bedroom floor with either ceramic porcelain tiles or wood angle click laminated flooring. They also had to find the cost of painting their bedroom walls. Students used the area of their bedroom and the area of the tiles to calculate the number of tiles (boxes) needed, as well as the cost of each type. Based on the cost, they indicated their preference. Similarly,

they used the area of the bedroom walls to determine the amount of paint and the cost of it. Their budget had to include all expenses for the renovation of the room, such as labour, brushes, grout, glue and rollers. The lecturer selected this task because it was a real-world scenario to which students could relate. Students had to use reasoning skills and apply formulas and were required to do accurate and realistic planning of the budget.

The second assignment involved advising a cardboard box manufacturing company on the most economical size of a box. Students had to adhere to specific requirements provided by the company, such as the volume, a square base and a top and bottom of double thickness. In this task, students made 3-D sketches of their proposed box and its 2-D shape that can be folded into the 3-D figure. They wrote equations for the volume, height and cost of the proposed box. Students also selected a suitable graph from which they could determine the minimum cost of the box. As a result, group members were able to advise the company on the most economical dimensions of the box. The reason for selecting this task was that students had to plan a strategy to tackle the problem, apply formulas, do calculations, sketch and interpret a graph, and make recommendations based on their solutions.

3.2.3 Data gathering and analysis

Data were generated by means of two assignments and tasked-based questions (see Table 1). In each assignment, students had to show all their calculations accompanied by their reasoning processes. Members had ample time to interact with each other, plan together, solve the problems and submit their best solutions via the group leaders. Thereafter, a total of nineteen students completed task-based questions on the two completed assignments. There were eleven questions regarding their initial feelings when confronted with the problems, the problem-solving strategies, knowledge and skills they applied, their experience of the problems, and the possible changes they would make if they had to complete the problems again. Members also reflected on how group work assisted or prevented them from achieving success. Data were coded with the aim of answering the research question. Both concept-driven coding (based on literature and/or initial list of codes) and data-driven coding (which emerged from the data) were used, and themes emerged from the data.

4 Results and Discussion

The researcher analysed the data and obtained the following initial list of codes: mathematics, group work, plans, challenges, reflections, experiences and feelings. The codes were refined further and the following five themes emerged, namely problem-solving approach, group collaboration, technology, real-world problems, reflection and challenges. Table 2 displays some reflections of students' active involvement in solving real-world problems. Quotations are presented verbatim and unedited. Participant numbers are indicated in brackets, e.g. [P-number].

Table 2. Students' reflections on their active participation in the problem-solving activities.

Aspect	Exemplars from responses by students
Problem-solving approach	A problem was given that needed to be analysed before it can be solved. I used the problem-solving skills that I am familiar with [P-3]
	I was uncertain what to do. I had to read through the problem a few times [P-2]
	No, initially I did not know how to solve the problem [P-7]
	I created my own measurements and researched about renovating materials [P-4]
	I used pictures to represent the problem [P-1]
Group collaboration	I drew a diagram and wrote everything down that was expected of me [P-2]
	I used critical thinking to write down equations that I could solve [P-3]
	It helped a lot to get more than one opinion or point of view on the solution to the problem [P-5]
	The ideas of the other students help your own ideas to grow [P-17]
	We could build on each other's ideas [P-13] and the others think about aspects that I do not think of [P-16]
Technology	I enjoyed to work together on the problems and to think about possible solutions and answers [P-6]
	Group work helped us because we could brainstorm together about the more challenging parts of the assignments [P-11]
	Group work helped me. There were three other people to ask for assistance when I struggled with something [P-1]
	I do not like group work, but I learned a lot from the others. Our team work made the 'dream work' [P-3]
Technology	I learned a lot from my fellow students [P-14]
	One of our group members did not do his part [P-5]
	Creating the ZOOM meetings was the most imperative part to share or communicate about the assignments [P-16]

	<p>The WhatsApp group helped us to communicate with each other regarding our planning, progress and challenges [P-15]</p> <p>We struggled to communicate with each other [P-10]</p> <p>The others were not always available [P-13]</p>
Real-world problems	<p>I enjoyed the problems and they did not feel like work. It was challenging at times, but that made the problems exciting [P-10]</p> <p>They were very insightful. I realised that the presentation of Mathematics need not always be boring and monotonous [P-9]</p> <p>I really enjoyed the problems as they forced me to think outside the box [P-8]</p> <p>They were good because I could learn a lot from them. They are applicable to the real world and that makes Mathematics more realistic and understandable [P-12]</p> <p>They made me look differently at Mathematics. It is not a static subject, but even school learners should solve real-world problems and not only hear about them [P-3]</p> <p>I could see that Mathematics is not just about numbers, but also about real life. The problems can be solved easily, but requires critical thinking [P-11]</p>
Reflection and challenges	<p>It was helpful to reflect. We could realise our mistakes, try different methods until we agreed on the solution [P-4]</p> <p>It was an experience to work with people that you do not know [P-4]</p> <p>My group members made me think. I would have been unable to find some of the answers without their assistance [P-15]</p> <p>The problems were interesting and showed me a lot regarding my own limitations [P-8]</p> <p>I had the opportunity to grow and realise that I am a good leader [P-8]</p> <p>It was challenging to study online and to communicate with the others [P-3]</p> <p>The fact that we were not together, was a tough hurdle to overcome [P-18] and since we were not around the campus due to COVID-19, most of us were struggling with internet connection [P-5]</p> <p>We struggled to adhere to our planning in order to submit the assignments on time [P-10] and I sometimes did not have data [P-1]</p>

The research question addressed in this section was: *how can active collaboration contribute to mathematics students' solving of real-world problems in an online environment?*

Students reflected positively on the contribution of online collaboration to their learning experiences, although they initially experienced some challenges in approaching a real-world problem (P-1, P-2, P-4, P-7) (see Table 2). Most members contributed to group work and enhanced their group dynamics. They used technologies, such as Zoom and WhatsApp, which enabled effective collaboration. Students were not only actively involved in their own learning (see Table 2), but also contributed to the learning of their peers. Members gained more than one point of view on the solution [P-5], they built on each other's mathematical ideas [P-13], and they thought deeply about aspects of real-world mathematics problems [P-16] and how to approach such problems. Furthermore, group members critically discussed and brainstormed the more challenging parts [P-11] and, as a result, they were forced to think outside the box [P-8]. For example, in the second assignment (card board box problem), many students thought that the graph should be a straight line, but it was a parabola. They could assist each other to solve this issue by selecting smaller values for the volume on the x-axis. In the process of achieving group goals, members assisted each other when they struggled [P-1], reflected on their problem-solving efforts, realised what their mistakes were, and used new ways to solve the mathematics problems [P-4]. Participant 15 explicitly stated, "[m]y group members made me think. I would have been unable to find some of the answers without their assistance." Regarding the value of addressing real-world mathematics problems, participants did not perceive mathematics to be monotonous [P-9] and expanded their views. They regarded such problems to be realistic, understandable [P-12] and insightful [P-9].

Active problem solvers also participate in mathematical reasoning, namely formulate, employ and interpret, as outlined by the OECD (2018). Examples are the following:

- students used mathematical reasoning to solve the problems (e.g. finding formulas for the volume and the cost of the box);
- they evaluated their solution by interpreting the results in terms of the initial situation (e.g. decided on the size of the most economical box based on their results and the given requirements); and
- students actively constructed new knowledge in solving these problems:
 - "I used critical thinking to write down equations that I could solve" [P-3]; and
 - "I drew a diagram and wrote everything down that was expected of me" [P-2].

These findings correspond with those by Farrow and Wetzel (2020) who state that active learning involves the facilitation of student collaboration as well as their participation in problem-solving activities. The online collaborative environment created a social presence in which students could participate effectively, communicate purposefully, and develop interpersonal relationships. A teaching presence, which involved the lecturer's design, facilitation and guidance of cognitive and social processes to achieve meaningful outcomes, was evident. Students could construct meaning through communication and reflection by means of their online collaboration. These findings correlate with the research by Carrillo and Flores (2020) who emphasise the importance of the above-mentioned three presences in an online collaborative environment (refer to section 2.2 above).

Some insights were gained regarding online learning. The teacher's presence assists students to feel secure in an active online environment. This provides adequate support and opportunities for constructive feedback. We suggest that real-world mathematics problems be related to students' experiences. Students were excited to solve real-world problems (e.g. renovate your bedroom), they were willing to take risks, and contributed to the success of the group. It was worthwhile for students to solve such problems as they could relate to the circumstances. However, a challenge in the online learning environment was the availability of data and the quality of the students' internet connection. These findings are in line with those of Mulenga and Marbán (2020) who indicated that prospective teachers experienced similar challenges when they engaged in online mathematics activities during the pandemic, for example some were unfamiliar with online platforms and often had no internet connection.

5 Conclusion

This research investigated the contribution of active online collaboration to mathematics students' solving of real-world problems during the COVID-19 pandemic. Results indicate that, although students experienced some challenges with the online learning environment, most benefited from their online collaboration. Students were actively involved in solving the problems and consequently developed new knowledge. They contributed to their own learning as well as to those of their peers. Students used to face-to-face environments had to adapt to student-centred teaching in an online environment where they had to become responsible for their own learning and for that of their team members. The contributions of the online collaboration were favourable despite the challenges that students experienced.

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